

EXERCISES THAT WILL HELP YOU IN RECOVERING FROM VEINS PROBLEM

Exercises are the best way to recover from the varicose veins. If you are going through a varicose veins problem, then you have to do regular exercise. This will help in reducing the chances of increasing varicose veins. The **vein doctor** guides you through the exercises that will reduce the symptoms of varicose veins and helps in improving your condition.

You must have to do some physical activities to recover from this, as exercise is not enough. The blood circulation in the legs increases when you do exercise this causes veins to pump healthy blood to the heart. Even a [vein doctor near me houston](#) says that physical activity helps in maintaining good body weight due to which vascular issues related to the body weight gets decreased.

Swimming: Swimming is an integral exercise for **varicose vein treatment**. In swimming, the movements of legs usually in the up and down direction which stops blood from pooling in them. This is the best low-impact cardio exercise as it does not require any kind of weight lifting which puts excess pressure on your legs. If you are a new learner then in that case you can start with 30 seconds and then you will take a 30-second break. Then you have to increase 10% week to week.

Walking: People who are taking **varicose vein treatment houston** advised to take long walking sessions daily. This walking session could be of 30 minutes a day to one hour a day. Walking is safe for all ages of people and it is extremely beneficial for people going through varicose veins. It maintains healthy blood circulation in the legs and provides strength to the muscles.

Yoga: In some poses of yoga, you elevate your legs above your heart which helps in maintaining a good blood flow. The main thing that yoga do is, helps you to focus on your breathing by some holding and stretching poses. Due to this reason, some **vein specialist near me** suggests you do yoga.

Cycling: According to **vein treatment Houston**, it is the easiest and smooth exercise to do. It will help in the movement of your joints and also improves blood circulation same as walking. You can improve your calf muscles and provide them good strength by doing regular cycling. In case, if you don't have a bicycle, then do not worry. You have to make a bicycling posture in which you have to bring your knees close to your chest and make a pedaling structure.

Ankle rotation: If you have to sit for a longer duration of time, then ankle rotation is a good exercise for [vein treatment](#). It encourages the blood to keep flowing in the feet and legs to the heart back. This improves your overall lower body blood circulation.

Step 1- Make small circles by rotating your feet at the ankles.

Step 2- Do this rotation in the opposite direction also and do it several times.